

1 **Changes in nutrient sensing during resistance to chemotherapy in TNBC.**

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8 Sestrin 2 was activated. Nutrient sensing secretory pathway component *TBC1D16* was mobilized.

9 Citations

10 1. Wolfson, R.L., Chantranupong, L., Saxton, R.A., Shen, K., Scaria, S.M., Cantor, J.R. and Sabatini,
11 D.M., 2016. Sestrin2 is a leucine sensor for the mTORC1 pathway. *Science*, 351(6268), pp.43-48.

12 2. Lee, J.H., Budanov, A.V., Talukdar, S., Park, E.J., Park, H.L., Park, H.W., Bandyopadhyay, G., Li,
13 N., Aghajan, M., Jang, I. and Wolfe, A.M., 2012. Maintenance of metabolic homeostasis by Sestrin2 and
14 Sestrin3. *Cell metabolism*, 16(3), pp.311-321.

15 3. Vizoso, M., Ferreira, H.J., Lopez-Serra, P., Carmona, F.J., Martinez-Cardus, A., Girotti, M.R.,
16 Villanueva, A., Guil, S., Moutinho, C., Liz, J. and Portela, A., 2015. Epigenetic activation of a cryptic
17 *TBC1D16* transcript enhances melanoma progression by targeting EGFR. *Nature medicine*, 21(7),
18 pp.741-750.